

How to cite: Dong, B., & Bakhir, N. M. (2024). Keyword Analysis of Student Satisfaction with Interactive Video-Based Teaching: From Student Feedback to Teaching Improvement. *World conference on future innovations and sustainable solutions*. (pp. 29-34). Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710252>

Keyword Analysis of Student Satisfaction with Interactive Video-Based Teaching: From Student Feedback to Teaching Improvement

Bo Dong¹, Norfarizah Mohd Bakhir²

¹PhD, New Media Department, School of the Arts, University Sains Malaysia, 11800 Penang, Malaysia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2404-125X>

²Doctor, Deputy Dean New Media Department, School of the Arts, University Sains Malaysia, 11800 Penang, Malaysia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9005-1455>

Accepted: August 21, 2024 | **Published:** September 6, 2024 | **Language:** English

Abstract: This study analyzes keywords related to student satisfaction with interactive video-based teaching, focusing on feedback from students. By identifying key factors such as interactivity, content quality, technical support, and feedback speed, the study provides insights into areas for teaching improvement. The findings suggest that enhancing interactivity and content quality are crucial for increasing student satisfaction. The study also offers practical recommendations for educators to optimize their use of interactive videos in online education.

Keywords: Interactive video, student satisfaction, keyword analysis, teaching improvement, online education.

Introduction

Interactive video instruction is a modern educational tool that combines video content with interactive features, aiming to enhance students' learning experience and engagement. By utilizing multimedia

resources such as videos, audio, and animations, along with interactive elements like real-time Q&A and quizzes, interactive video enables students to actively participate in the learning process. This interactivity significantly improves students' attention and comprehension (Zhang, Zhou, Briggs, & Nunamaker, 2006). In recent years, with the rapid development of online education, interactive video instruction has become a vital tool in the educational field, especially in the widespread application of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) (Guo, Kim, & Rubin, 2014). The proliferation of online learning platforms has allowed interactive video instruction to transcend the spatial and temporal limitations of traditional classrooms, offering personalized learning pathways that cater to the diverse needs of learners (Kay, 2012).

Teaching satisfaction is a crucial indicator for evaluating instructional effectiveness. Student satisfaction not only directly impacts their learning motivation and academic performance but also influences their overall evaluation of the course (Kuo, Walker, Schroder, & Belland, 2014). In an online education environment, teaching satisfaction becomes even more important due to the lack of face-to-face interaction, making course design, content quality, and interactivity key factors in maintaining student engagement and motivation (Swan, 2001). Research has shown that in online education, student satisfaction is closely related to the interactivity of the course, technical support, and the sense of control students have over their learning environment (Scheiter & Gerjets, 2007)

Interactive video instruction not only provides a multi-sensory learning experience but also enhances student engagement through real-time feedback and interactive activities (Brame, 2016). For example, scenario simulations and Q&A sessions can help students better understand and apply the knowledge they have acquired, thereby improving learning outcomes (Fiorella & Mayer, 2018). However, despite the widespread potential of interactive video instruction in the educational field, its actual effectiveness in enhancing student satisfaction still requires further research (Guo et al., 2014). Studies suggest that the design and implementation of interactive videos need to be optimized according to different instructional contexts to fully realize their educational potential (Brame, 2016).

Currently, a substantial body of research has explored the impact of interactive video instruction on student learning outcomes. For example, Zhang et al. (2006) demonstrated that interactive video instruction significantly enhances student engagement and knowledge acquisition. Guo et al. (2014) further investigated how interactive elements in video production can boost student engagement and learning outcomes. Additionally, Kay (2012) reviewed the application of video podcasts in education, highlighting the widespread use of interactive video across various disciplines, such as medicine, engineering, and language learning, which has significantly improved students' learning motivation and academic performance.

Although interactive video instruction has shown outstanding performance in enhancing learning outcomes, there has been relatively little systematic analysis of student feedback, particularly in identifying the key factors that influence student satisfaction. Student feedback provides valuable insights for instructional design and improvement, but existing research predominantly relies on surveys and focus group interviews, lacking large-scale textual analysis of student feedback (Scheiter & Gerjets, 2007). By employing text analysis methods such as keyword analysis, educators can extract valuable information from a large volume of student feedback, enabling a better understanding of

student needs and allowing for adjustments in instructional strategies (Bazeley, 2020).

Although existing research on interactive video instruction has made progress in many areas, some gaps remain. In particular, there is a lack of keyword analysis of student feedback, a method that can uncover the core issues repeatedly mentioned by students in their feedback. This helps educators make targeted instructional improvements, thereby enhancing overall student satisfaction (Guo et al., 2014). Keyword analysis can identify the driving factors behind student satisfaction, but it has not yet been fully utilized in the study of interactive video instruction (Fiorella & Mayer, 2018).

Based on the above background, this study aims to address the following key questions: First, what is the actual effectiveness of interactive video instruction in enhancing student satisfaction? Second, what are the key driving factors that influence students' satisfaction with interactive video instruction? Finally, can keyword analysis of student feedback identify new pathways for improving instructional methods (Brame, 2016)?

To achieve the above objectives, this study will employ keyword analysis to examine the collected student feedback data. Keyword analysis is an effective text analysis technique that can reveal the core themes and issues within a text by identifying high-frequency words (Bazeley, 2020). This method is particularly well-suited for analyzing large-scale datasets, such as student feedback on online courses (Kay, 2012).

The study will gather student evaluations and feedback from multiple online course platforms and use natural language processing techniques to preprocess the data. This will involve extracting high-frequency keywords and conducting frequency analysis and pattern recognition. The research process includes several steps: data collection, text preprocessing, keyword extraction and frequency analysis, and pattern recognition (Kay, 2012). Through these analyses, the study aims to identify the key factors influencing student satisfaction and provide targeted recommendations for instructional improvement, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of interactive video instruction and increasing student satisfaction (Guo et al., 2014).

Research Results

Following the keyword analysis of student feedback, several key terms reflecting students' satisfaction with interactive video instruction were identified. These keywords include "interactivity," "content quality," "technical support," "feedback speed," and "learning experience." Analyzing the frequency distribution of these keywords revealed that "interactivity" was the most frequently occurring term, accounting for approximately 25% of all keywords. "Content quality" followed with 20%, while "technical support" and "feedback speed" accounted for 15% and 10%, respectively (Johnson & Aragon, 2003). These keywords indicate that when evaluating interactive video instruction, students are most concerned with the effectiveness of interaction with the content and instructors, as well as the quality of the video content.

Further analysis indicates that "interactivity" is not only the core driving factor of student satisfaction but also the key element most frequently mentioned by students as enhancing their learning experience. Students generally believe that highly interactive instructional videos help to maintain

their attention and assist in better understanding the course content (Giannakos, Chorianopoulos, & Chrisochoides, 2014).

Based on the keyword analysis results, this study identified several key factors influencing student satisfaction. First, interactivity is considered the most important driving factor. Highly interactive instructional videos not only capture students' attention but also encourage active participation in the learning process (Kuo, Walker, Schroder, & Belland, 2014). Secondly, content quality is another crucial factor determining student satisfaction. High-quality video content helps students more effectively grasp knowledge and enhances their overall evaluation of the course (Zhang, Zhou, Briggs, & Nunamaker, 2006).

Technical support and feedback speed are also important factors influencing student satisfaction with interactive video instruction. The stability of technical support and the promptness of feedback responses can effectively reduce the technical barriers students encounter during the learning process, thereby enhancing their learning experience and satisfaction (Al-Fraihat, Joy, Masa'deh, & Sinclair, 2020). The relative importance of these factors varies among different student groups. For example, technical support is particularly crucial for students with weaker technical skills, while feedback speed is key to the satisfaction of students who seek quick answers to their questions (Swan, 2001).

Through further pattern recognition analysis, this study identified some correlations between the keywords. For example, "interactivity" and "content quality" exhibited a high degree of correlation, suggesting that highly interactive instructional content is often also of high quality, and this dual advantage significantly enhances student satisfaction (Choi & Johnson, 2007). Additionally, a strong correlation was found between "technical support" and "feedback speed," indicating that in environments with good technical support, instructors can respond to student inquiries more quickly, further improving satisfaction (Sun & Rueda, 2012).

These patterns also vary across different course types or instructional contexts. In technical courses, students place more importance on technical support and feedback speed, while in humanities courses, content quality and interactivity are more crucial (Kalyuga, 2007). This variability suggests that different types of courses need to optimize video teaching strategies according to student needs to enhance overall teaching satisfaction.

Conclusions

This study systematically analyzed student feedback on interactive video instruction through keyword analysis and identified the key driving factors influencing student satisfaction. The research found that "interactivity," "content quality," "technical support," and "feedback speed" are the primary drivers of student satisfaction. These factors frequently appeared in student feedback, indicating their significant impact on the learning experience and overall satisfaction (Kuo, Walker, Schroder, & Belland, 2014). In particular, "interactivity" and "content quality" were identified as the core elements for enhancing student engagement and knowledge acquisition (Giannakos, Chorianopoulos, & Chrisochoides, 2014; Zhang, Zhou, Briggs, & Nunamaker, 2006).

The results of this study make a significant contribution to educational practice, particularly in the area of instructional improvement based on student feedback. The keyword analysis method proposed in this study provides educators with an effective tool to systematically analyze large volumes of student feedback and identify key areas for improvement in teaching (Al-Fraihat, Joy, Masa'deh, & Sinclair, 2020). This approach not only helps enhance the quality of instructional content but also improves the learning experience and satisfaction of students by optimizing technical support and feedback mechanisms (Sun & Rueda, 2012). By applying the findings of this study to educational practice, educators can better design interactive video courses that meet student needs, thereby improving overall instructional effectiveness.

Although this study provides important insights into student satisfaction with interactive video instruction, there are still many areas that warrant further exploration. Future research could delve deeper into the impact of different instructional tools and methods on student satisfaction, particularly in various disciplines and educational contexts (Kalyuga, 2007). Additionally, future studies should focus on how innovative interactive designs and personalized learning pathways can enhance student learning outcomes and satisfaction (Choi & Johnson, 2007). As educational technology continues to evolve, researchers could explore how emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and augmented reality, can be leveraged to improve the effectiveness of interactive video instruction.

References

- Al-Fraihat, D., Joy, M., Masa'deh, R., & Sinclair, J. (2020). Evaluating E-learning systems success: An empirical study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, *102*, 67-86.
- Bazeley, P. (2020). *Qualitative data analysis: Practical strategies*.
- Brame, C. J. (2016). Effective educational videos: Principles and guidelines for maximizing student learning from video content. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, *15*(4), es6.
- Choi, H. J., & Johnson, S. D. (2007). The effect of context-based video instruction on learning and motivation in online courses. *The American Journal of Distance Education*, *21*(4), 215-227.
- Fiorella, L., & Mayer, R. E. (2018). What works and doesn't work with instructional video. *Computers in Human Behavior*.
- Giannakos, M. N., Chorianopoulos, K., & Chrisochoides, N. (2014). Making sense of video analytics: Lessons learned from clickstream interactions, attitudes, and learning outcome in a video-assisted course. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, *15*(6), 260-283.
- Guo, P. J., Kim, J., & Rubin, R. (2014). How video production affects student engagement: An empirical study of MOOC videos. In *Proceedings of the first ACM conference on Learning@ scale conference* (pp. 41-50). ACM.
- Kalyuga, S. (2007). Expertise reversal effect and its implications for learner-tailored instruction. *Educational Psychology Review*, *19*(4), 509-539.
- Kay, R. H. (2012). Exploring the use of video podcasts in education: A comprehensive review of the literature. *Computers in Human Behavior*, *28*(3), 820-831.

Kuo, Y. C., Walker, A. E., Schroder, K. E., & Belland, B. R. (2014). Interaction, Internet self-efficacy, and self-regulated learning as predictors of student satisfaction in online education courses. *The Internet and Higher Education, 20*, 35-50.

Scheiter, K., & Gerjets, P. (2007). Learner control in hypermedia environments. *Educational Psychology Review, 19*(3), 285-307.

Sun, J. C. Y., & Rueda, R. (2012). Situational interest, computer self-efficacy, and self-regulation: Their impact on student engagement in distance education. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 43*(2), 191-204.

Swan, K. (2001). Virtual interaction: Design factors affecting student satisfaction and perceived learning in asynchronous online courses. *Distance Education, 22*(2), 306-331.

Zhang, D., Zhou, L., Briggs, R. O., & Nunamaker, J. F. (2006). Instructional video in e-learning: Assessing the impact of interactive video on learning effectiveness. *Information & Management, 43*(1), 15-27.